

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Overcoming Old Age Related Digital Divide Using Inclusive Libraries Services

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Abstract

The rise in technological advancement brought a shift in skills requirement and competence in technologies usage, leaving the older adults at disadvantage and at the fringe of the technological revolution. This study explores how libraries - both public and academic can create opportunities for bridging this divide, often referred to as grey digital divide, with intergenerational programs and approaches. This can help them develop some required skills, create equity, inclusivity for the older adults in terms of access to information on digital platforms and in addition, motivate their interests in technological trends, build confidence, improve skill sets for lifelong mastering of technological development. The study employed literature review to enhance better understanding of prior work in the field, thus focus was on older adults' technologies usage, library services for older adults (+65) and intergenerational programs in libraries in the African context. Findings showed intergenerational approach can greatly support older adults to overcome personal challenges to embrace the use of digital technologies. However, library intervention in the form intergenerational programs can bridge the gap, through enabling environment needs to be created. The study recommends policies that promotes creative innovation of programmes in the libraries that can meet the interest of both older adults and young people for a successful intergenerational program.

Keywords: Grey Digital Divide, Intergenerational Programs, Digital Literacy, Older Adults, Inclusivity.

1. Introduction

The world's population is ageing rapidly with people living longer because of technological advancement and improved health (Bennett-Kapusniak, 2018). However, older people are

finding themselves isolated and socially excluded due to their inability to cope with the technological advancement, with the whole world now depending on technology (Barrie et al., 2021). As such their incompetence in terms of internet access or the use of technologies and

absence of required skills is a noticeable barrier (Golenko et al., 2020). This became visible especially during the Covid-19 pandemic and contributed to their feeling of depression and other mental health issues among other things, regarded as grey digital divide (Alexopoulou, Astrom & Karlsson, 2022). Thus, the need to come up with ways to boost their welfare, independence and social inclusion through technology use becomes paramount (Peleg-Adler, Lanir & Kornan 2018).

As part of the ways of developing older adults inclusion and independence through technologies (bridging the grey digital divide), libraries, as knowledge and information powerhouses, can play their role in provision of opportunities through public and academic libraries by participation in learning programmes based on experiences with intergenerational work, which would bring young and older adult together to develop social networks that can help motivate their interests and also create an avenue for lifelong learning opportunities for the older adults (Sabo 2017; Leong et al., 2021). To this effect, offering intergenerational programs in libraries can encourage interactions between generations while boosting older adults' interest in partaking in learning activities capable of creating social relationships that can support both physically and emotionally (Baluk, Griffin & Gillet, 2021).

Intergenerational program involves bringing young people within a community to increase

interaction, to meet older adults with the intend of forming close bond to develop relationship, social networks and connections between different the different age that can be beneficial to both generations (Yarker, 2021).

Libraries around the world like the Canadian Urban Library Council (CULC), Toronto Public Library, Crystal Lake Public Library, Illinois offer some form of intergenerational programmes like virtual reality storytelling (VRCHIVE), book club, board game café, knitting circles, writing groups, computer training and so on (Baluk, Griffin & Gillet 2021; Dalmer & Mitrovica, 2022). This is not common practice in African libraries, as they are yet to embrace or adopt this type of programmes in their libraries to help the large growing number of older adults in the society.

This study intends to explore ways intergenerational programmes can be introduced into to the African library context with the hope of bringing awareness as to how the programme can support or assist older adults in developing interest and achieving lifelong learning as well as overcoming uncertainty on ways of accessing information especially on digital platforms. There had been consistent studies covering library services for older adults in the 70's, 90's and early 2000's but over the years little especially in Africa. Although recently the studies are beginning to pick up again. There is still limited literature on library services for older adults using intergenerational programmes

within the African context. This study hopes to bridge the gap.

Ageing comes with general slowing of cognitive processes, decreased memory capacity, decreased attentional control, and difficulty in goal maintenance (Charness & Boot 2022). Ageing as a natural process occurs at very fast pace in the society just as birth rate is declining (WHO, 2025; Golenko et al., 2020). Ageing involves general slowing of cognitive processes, decreased memory capacity, decreased attentional control, and difficulty staying focused even on little tasks (Charness & Boot, 2022).

This makes older adults quite vulnerable and at higher risks to illness and underlying health conditions as physiological and cognitive decline begins to take a toll on them (Bakshi & Bhattacharyya, 2021; WHO 2025; Cerrito et al., 2015). They have trouble in performing daily activities because their motor and sensory systems deteriorate, resulting in decreased mobility and functional ability leaving them as dependants (Yap et al., 2022).

However, using intergenerational programs, libraries can motivate and spark the older adults interest using selected activities to steer their attention to the increasing amount of quality information online on literacy as well as health awareness which libraries can make accessible and thus inspire them to use technologies in seeking and using information (Manzuch & Maceviute, 2020).

The following constitute the purpose of the study:

1. An overview of technology use by older adults
2. Exploration of Library services for older adults- specifically in African library context
3. Using intergenerational program to support to older adults in African Libraries.

2. Literature Review

The literature review is based on the purpose of the study which include overview of technology use by older adults, library services for older adults and use of intergenerational program to support older adults in libraries.

2.1 Older Adults Technology Usage

Digital technology usage enhances older adults' quality of life and helps keep them active through frequent interactions with family, peers and friend online (Arthanat et al., 2019; Huh & Seo, 2015). However, complex feature of some devices makes some adults to show no interest in the use.

Mobile technologies, wearable technologies and social network can enhance quality of life for older adults by uplifting their moods, enabling them to access health information, manage symptoms, communicate with health providers, and loved ones hence creating inclusion (Andrews et al., 2019; Senteio, 2019; Francis et al., 2019). However, older adults have been observed not to use technology as much as other generations (Bangert et al., 2022).

Wilson (2018) alludes to the fact that loneliness is a major issue that confronts older adults and the best way to curb it is through active engagement within their social circle using mobile technologies, as most are unable to actively engage socially due to illness, mobility and disability issues. This is supported by Khalili-Mahani and Sawchuk (2022) who noted the challenges embedded in the use of ICT by older adults' stem from personal factors like fear of stigmatization, dependency, technophobia etc. The study also observed that modifying the technologies to fit individual needs enhances acceptance (Khalili-Mahani & Sawchuk, 2022).

In their study, Haase et al., (2024) found that most older adults use of digital technologies is based on peer usage so as not to be left out and to maintain social connection. Although Elimelech et al., (2022) on the other hand observed in their study between Spain, France and Israel that majority older adults' own smartphones because they found it useful for their everyday life activities not because of peer usage. Technology use in older adults' is linked with race/ethnicity, marital status, gender, employment status, and social and physical activity as well as health related issues especially for the purpose of keeping abreast with their health status (Kim et al., 2020).

In a study by Izadi-Avanji and Darki (2020) to measure older adults' behavioural activities, knowledge in the use of technology, to improve and support independent living. The study noted

the gap in the use of technologies by older adults in different countries and their activities are mostly limited to the use of television remote. Because most are hindered from using other digital appliances in their homes because of absence of skills, knowledge and the complexity of some of the appliances.

Most older adults find it difficult accepting or using new technologies especially when it is hard to use (Senteio, 2019). Many of them cannot make use of some of the features on mobile technology as they appeared to be too complex for their level of knowledge as such it defeats their cognitive abilities (Leburu, Grobler & Bohman, 2018). This complexity with the use of technology makes most of them passive towards technology usage (Charness & Boot, 2022).

The declining physical cognitive abilities, mental and emotional barrier make some older adults afraid of using technologies so that they do not make mistakes while handling technology, as such it becomes a challenge and they get discouraged from using technologies (Freeman et al., 2022; Lee & Kim 2019; Dumrongsiri, 2022; Bohman, 2018; Cheng et al., 2021). All the changes, couple with the feeling of incompetence, with little or no skills in using technology leads to anxiety and less motivation in performing information search online (Golenko et al., 2020; Bennett-Kapusniak, 2018). This is supported by Chen (2020) who participants in his study reported feeling anxiety towards the use of digital technologies like

mobile devices due to the complex interface, that make them confused.

Older adults' inability to access or use of digital technologies mean older adults are deprived of resources that can support their aging gracefully in a technological advanced society (Francis et al., 2019). As such they require support on the use of technologies which is not readily available (Mubarak & Suomi 2022).

This calls for the need to pursue older adults' inclusiveness through library services in their role to support older adults' abilities to use technologies for information (Mubarak & Nycyk 2017; Oduor, 2021). Although cultural and social context and in certain societies might serve as set back to older adults' ability to easily learn or use technologies as some cultures discourage that (Rosales & Blanche-T, 2022).

2.2 Library Services for Older Adults

Older adults like everyone in the society have information needs as such access and use of information should be made a priority (Kuscus & Fombad, 2017). And the library has the role of supporting lifelong learning to increase social inclusion especially for individuals with challenges (Majinge & Stillwell, 2014). This need as identified by the American Library Association in 1957 prompted the publication of a handbook on library services for older adults in 1961 (Lenstra, Oguz & Duvall, 2019). As well as a guideline for library services to older adults in

1972 that had since been revised thrice (1987, 1999 & 2008).

Some of the guidelines include:

- ✓ Staff training to help older adults with courtesy and respect.
- ✓ Information Services and Collections that reflects the needs of older adults.
- ✓ Organizing programs should be targeted more senior population interest and needs.
- ✓ Provision of IT related services and assisting and teaching about IT to the older adults etc.

In the same vein, the Canadian Federation of Library Associations (CFLA) having understood biases aimed at older adult, discourages any form of negativity towards them create awareness to libraries on the need to first identified their diversity, to be mindful of the dangers of stereotyping when planning library collection, programs and services.

In Japan, library services for older adults are categorized under services for disabled, presumably to show that it is meant for people with special needs and require special attention (Uda et al., 2018). Meaning libraries across the globe are awakening to the increasing need to provide older adults with special services in the library. In Ontario, public library offers digital literacy training for older adults in addition with necessary support and explanation needed to overcome their anxiety and fear when using information technology.

Some libraries in their attempt to make relevant information accessible and available to users like older adults who are also patients, they go the extra mile to team with health practitioners to make it happen, for example the collaboration between the Inova Fairfax Health Sciences Library and the hospital's Geriatrics Team (Culler, Heisy & Crantz, 2013). The resources are specially geared for older adults like large print books, assistive devices, adapted workstation equipped with ZoomText software and a large-print keyboard and the likes. This is because having access to information and especially health information can give older adults better understanding of their condition and the treatment options (Senteio, 2019).

In Cuba, public libraries create awareness in older adults through literacy programs on different stages in aging enable them to be ready with knowledge of what to be expected and how to care of their health. For example, the public libraries of San Antonio de Los Banos organizes and host conversation in old people's homes on "how to enjoy a healthy and happy old age, promotes books, and organizes memory-protecting exercises sessions (de Armas, 2019).

In South Africa, the constitution recognizes the need to empower older adults by making right for them to have access to relevant information (RSA 2006). This can also be reflected in our libraries throughout the continent. Even the International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions' / UNESCO 1994 manifesto

support older adults' inclusiveness, as it noted the library 'as a living force for education, culture and information' should encourage equality of access for all, regardless of age

Charbonneau (2014) in her study, noted many public libraries are beginning to make their websites older adults' accessibility friendly to meet their need through provision of suitable services. And concluded that creating awareness on accessibility of website to older adults in libraries will be valuable at the long run.

Libraries can come up with models to identify not just the obstacles older adults face but also ways of supporting and helping them overcome such obstacles (ALA150,2026). One of such ways or medium of overcoming such obstacles or challenges for the older adults in the libraries can be through the introduction of intergenerational programmes in the library.

To this regard, libraries irrespective of the type must be geared towards planning services for older adults within the community they serve (Bennett-Kapusniak, 2018). Because according to Kesselman (2019) libraries serve as enabler for users in achieving important things because they create opportunities for creativity as well as enhancing skills of its users from all works of life and age, enabling them to meet their different needs. In this situation, libraries can enhance the intellectual, social, and general well-being of older adults (Meyer & Worster, 2015).

2.3 Using Intergenerational Programme in Libraries

Intergenerational programme is the engaging of younger adults in mentoring and giving older adults needed support otherwise known as reverse mentoring, a term with origin business world (Breck, Dennis & Leedahl, 2018).

Senteio (2019) observed that involving older adults with young adults can be effective because it enables them to unite around a specific topic, such as technology use. Older adults rely on the younger adult to support them with the functions that they could not manage due to lack of technical skills (Steyn, Roos & Botha, 2018). The bond form from the intergenerational relationship can serve as a medium of social support and increase the retention rate in older adults.

Intergenerational programmes enhance accessibility for older adults as well as increases activities and space for social inclusion (Nelischer & Loukaitou-Sideris, 2022). This explains why libraries like Toronto Public Library developed an intergenerational program using digital storytelling during the pandemic to help address isolation and loneliness. Digital storytelling can facilitate social connectedness in older adults while helping to build their digital literacy (Hausknecht et al., 2021:).

Intergenerational programmes assist older adults to overcome age related stereotype like the grey

digital divide is through the intergenerational program (Santini et al., 2018). This can assist in teaching older adults' digital literacy, which in turn can improvement older adults physical, cognitive, psychological and social wellbeing (Simionata, 2023). Meaning intergeneration program can be very effective in overcoming the grey digital divide.

3. Methodology

The study used literature review as a method which is a way of collecting and synthesising previous research which when done effectively creates a firm foundation for advancing knowledge and facilitating theory development (Snyder, 2019). In addition, Literature reviews can enhance researchers understanding of prior work in their field, thus enable them to easily identify gaps in the body of literature and potential avenues for future research (Kraus et al., 2022). Articles related to older adults' use of technologies, library services and intergenerational program were carefully identified, and were gathered to find suitable ways of providing services to meet up with older adults' information needs in the present technological time.

To be able to carry that out, articles were selected from notable databases like ProQuest, EBSCOhost, Scopus, Web of Science, Google Scholar as well as University of Pretoria library database.

Search strategy: Search was conducted between the period of June 2023 – October 2023. Over one hundred articles were obtained but only fifty-nine articles were used. The selection of articles was based on the purposes of the study, and themes found during the article search include “technology use by older adults”, “library services for older adults in Africa”, “using intergenerational programme in libraries to support older adults”.

Search term: “older adults technology use” “library services for older adults” “intergenerational programs in library”.

Inclusion/exclusion: articles included in the use of technologies were based on older adults (+60), elderly and seniors and written in English language. Articles with populations lesser than +60 and in other languages were excluded.

4. Discussion

The aim of this article was to explore how libraries-both public and academic in the African context can create opportunities of bridging the grey digital divide. The findings from this study shows that the divide is creating more challenges for older adults, depriving them of benefits of using technologies and leaving them in exclusion and in isolation. To properly tackle the menace of the grey digital divide, there is the need for libraries to understand ageing process and personal barriers which comes with aging and

leads to the grey divide and develop proper solution.

However, for libraries to adopt this approach it is necessary to put into consideration the vulnerable state of older adults’ physical health and psychological and mental wellbeing and create a conducive as well as accessible space where both generations can meet, bond and interact and gradually be assisted in accepting and using technologies (Bakshi & Bhattacharyya 2021; Yarker, 2021; WHO 2025).

Libraries can give them a sense of belonging and purpose as well as inclusivity in their advanced age, while uplifting their moods and providing the right atmosphere for interaction and sharing relevant information like health tips among themselves (de Armas 2019; Roos, 2022). In addition, it can be an avenue not only to teach digital literacy to older adults’ but also to create awareness on advantages or benefits that comes with the use of technologies, while offering them hands on experiences.

5. Conclusion

To this end, libraries can create activities to engage the different generations with intellectual activities like memory games and physical activities to enhances cognitive vitality and at the end older participants can feel emotionally supported and socially accepted, while the younger generation get enlighten on how to be supportive towards the older generation Thus the

older adults will be motivated into picking interest and learning new ideas like technology use for information access

The ability of libraries in Africa to tailor their services towards the needs of older adults using intergenerational approach will go a long way in supporting lifelong learning which is crucial for facing today's challenges and giving older adults inclusivity in the digital technological era.

6. Recommendations

- ✓ Adequate planning for designing a conducive space, equipped with relevant technologies to assist and support older adults needs to be put in place.
- ✓ Libraries can launch older adults' programmes which can be in the form of weekly activities that encompass their interests such as book clubs for the older adults some older adults love recreational reading, libraries can establish activities to meet their different leisure information needs
- ✓ Activities like gardening, quilting and Jewellery making, storytelling, digital diary creation should be introduced in the libraries for older adults.
- ✓ Library administrators and policy makers need to take into the cognizance the increasing population of older adults which calls for considerations in services specifically tailored to meet their information needs.

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